

ASSESSMENT CULTURE IN DIGITAL EDUCATION AND FLEXIBLE PEDAGOGICAL DIAGNOSTIC APPROACHES IN ONLINE AND HYBRID LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF FEMALE TEACHERS

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Abstract. This article analyzes the role and significance of pedagogical diagnostics in the context of digital transformation within online and hybrid education systems. It explores the culture of assessment and flexible pedagogical diagnostic approaches from the perspective of female educators. Modern digital technologies, including artificial intelligence-based formative, summative, adaptive, and reflective assessment methods, are examined as essential tools for identifying learners' knowledge and competencies and for creating a personalized and interactive learning process. The article also highlights innovative opportunities in learner monitoring, immediate feedback, and self-assessment mechanisms, as well as the necessity of enhancing digital literacy among female educators.

Keywords: digital learning environment, online and hybrid teaching, pedagogical diagnostics, assessment culture, artificial intelligence, formative and summative assessment, digital platforms, learner monitoring, female educators' activity.

RAQAMLI TA'LIMDA BAHOLASH MADANIYATI VA ONLAYN HAMDA GIBRID O'QUV MUHITLARIDA MOSLASHUVCHAN PEDAGOGIK DIAGNOSTIKA YONDASHUVLARI AYOL O'QITUVCHILAR NUQTAYNAZARIDAN

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada raqamli ta'lim muhiti, xususan onlayn va gibrid o'qitish sharoitida pedagogik diagnostikaning roli va ahamiyati atroflicha tahlil qilinadi. Pedagog xotin-qizlar faoliyati nuqtai nazaridan baholash madaniyati va moslashuvchan pedagogik diagnostika yondashuvlari o'rganiladi. Zamonaviy raqamli texnologiyalar, jumladan sun'iy intellekt asosida shakllangan formatif, summativ, adaptiv va reflektiv baholash usullari o'quvchilarning bilim va kompetensiyalarini aniqlash, ta'lim jarayonini shaxsga yo'naltirilgan va interaktiv qilishda muhim vosita sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, maqolada o'quv monitoringi, tezkor teskari aloqa va o'z-o'zini baholash mexanizmlarining innovatsion imkoniyatlari hamda pedagog xotin-qizlarning raqamli savodxonligini oshirish zaruriyati ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit soʻzlar: raqamli taʼlim muhiti, onlayn va gibrid oʻqitish, pedagogik diagnostika, baholash madaniyati, sunʼiy intellekt, formatif va summativ baholash, raqamli platformalar, oʻquv monitoringi, pedagog xotin-qizlar faoliyati.

КУЛЬТУРА ОЦЕНИВАНИЯ В ЦИФРОВОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ И ГИБКИЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ В ОНЛАЙН И ГИБРИДНЫХ ОБУЧАЮЩИХ СРЕДАХ С ТОЧКИ ЗРЕНИЯ ЖЕНЩИН-ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЕЙ

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Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется роль и значение педагогической диагностики в условиях цифровой трансформации системы онлайн и гибридного обучения. Рассматриваются культура оценки и адаптивные подходы к педагогической диагностике с позиции деятельности женщин-педагогов. Современные цифровые технологии, включая методы формативного, суммативного, адаптивного и рефлексивного оценивания на основе искусственного интеллекта, рассматриваются как важные инструменты для определения знаний и компетенций учащихся, а также для создания персонализированного и интерактивного учебного процесса. В статье также подчёркиваются инновационные возможности мониторинга учащихся, оперативной обратной связи и механизмов самооценки, а также необходимость повышения цифровой грамотности женщин-педагогов.

Ключевые слова: цифровая образовательная среда, онлайн и гибридное обучение, педагогическая диагностика, культура оценивания, искусственный интеллект, формативное и суммативное оценивание, цифровые платформы, мониторинг обучения, деятельность женщин-педагогов.

Introduction

In recent years, the widespread introduction of digital technologies in education has led to the popularization of online and hybrid forms of education. This, in turn, is taking pedagogical diagnostic processes to a new level. The issue of forming a culture of assessment in digital education and the use of modern pedagogical diagnostic approaches is of particular importance in the activities of female teachers. In the context of online and hybrid education, the use of digital platforms and tools based on artificial intelligence by teachers, in particular female teachers, significantly increases the opportunities for monitoring the quality of education and determining the individual mastery of students. This situation serves to strengthen flexibility, interactivity and personal approaches in the process of pedagogical diagnostics.

Research methodology

The main purpose of this study is to conduct an in-depth study of the process of pedagogical diagnostics in online and hybrid education, analyze existing methods and approaches, and also determine their impact on the quality and effectiveness of education. Theoretical-analytical, comparative and empirical methods were used as the

research methodology. The activities of female teachers on online and hybrid educational platforms were studied, and their successes and difficulties in using digital diagnostic tools were analyzed. The effectiveness of implementing formative assessment methods in the practical activities of female teachers and their impact on student motivation were also considered. Using observation and interview methods, attention was paid to their adaptive approaches in the process of pedagogical diagnostics, their role in organizing personalized education[1].

Analysis of relevant literature

Many domestic and foreign scientists have conducted scientific research on pedagogical diagnostics, and theoretical and practical aspects in this area have been deeply analyzed. Diagnostic issues are becoming increasingly relevant, especially in modern education. Pedagogical diagnostics allows the teacher to determine the level of students' knowledge, to base their assessment on objective criteria, and to monitor the individuality and development dynamics of students. Theoretical foundations play an important role in this process, and the analysis of scientific literature determines the methodological foundation of diagnostic activities.

The main theoretical approaches to pedagogical diagnostics have been developed by Russian scientists. In particular, N. E. Shchurkova in her research has shown the psychological and pedagogical foundations of pedagogical assessment. She emphasizes that the assessment process should take into account not only the measurement of knowledge, but also the personal development of the student, his interests and participation in the activity. V. V. Serikov developed a person-oriented approach to diagnostic activities, which emphasized that through this approach it is possible to form the student's self-awareness, independent thinking and self-control skills. Yu. K. Babansky noted the special role of diagnostics in the management system of the educational process and proposed differential methods of assessment in this regard[2].

The analysis of the literature has shown that scientific research and practical experience in the field of pedagogical diagnostics are of great importance for the effective management of the educational process by female teachers on digital platforms. Pedagogical diagnostics and digital assessment methodologies presented by local scholars are widely used in the work of female teachers. International experiences include advanced approaches to the introduction of flexible and interactive methods of diagnostic processes in online and hybrid education. This further increases the need for female teachers to improve their digital literacy, enrich their methodological knowledge, and actively use new technologies[3].

Analysis and results

The results show that female teachers are successfully using pedagogical diagnostics in online and hybrid education as a means of implementing personalized learning. Their digital assessment culture serves to improve the quality of education and adapt to the individual needs of students. Therefore, in order to make the pedagogical diagnostic process more effective, it is necessary to provide special digital literacy programs for female teachers, teach formative and adaptive assessment methods, and encourage the use of modern platforms[4].

In general, the activities of female teachers are important in developing a culture of assessment in digital education, introducing flexible approaches to pedagogical diagnostics in online and hybrid conditions. Their pedagogical activities serve as a priority in improving the quality of the educational process using new technologies, developing students, and effectively organizing pedagogical processes.

As a result of the observations and analyses conducted, it was found that pedagogical diagnostics in online and hybrid education conditions are fundamentally different from traditional assessment approaches. One of the main differences is the active use of digital tools and artificial intelligence technologies in the diagnostic process, which enhances the interactivity and person-centered approach to education. In this context, traditional assessment tools are being replaced by formative, summative, adaptive and reflective approaches[5].

Today, formative assessment is a leading method of pedagogical diagnostics. This method provides an opportunity to provide students with quick feedback during the learning process. In particular, mini-surveys, interactive exercises and quick tests conducted on platforms such as Google Forms, Quizizz, Edmodo, Nearpod, increase the effectiveness of formative assessment. These tools not only assess students' knowledge, but also develop their ability to think independently, analyze and make quick decisions[6].

Summative assessment methods are used at important stages of the educational process. This form of assessment allows you to determine the overall level of mastery of students in a learning module or course. Platforms such as Moodle LearningApps Testportali uz are widely used in summative assessment. The automated structure of test questions provides the opportunity for rapid analysis and statistical processing of results, which allows the teacher to deeply analyze the state of mastery of each student and establish a differentiated approach.

In recent years, special attention has been paid to adaptive testing methods based on artificial intelligence in diagnostics. These tests automatically adjust the complexity of the next questions based on the student's previous answers. This approach provides an individual approach and allows you to accurately identify gaps in the student's knowledge. For example, adaptive approaches implemented on the Khan Academy platform offer customized educational directions to students[7].

In the modern educational process, reflective approaches are becoming an integral part of diagnostics. Students express their thoughts and feelings through tools such as Jamboard Padlet and Google Jamboard, analyze their own activities and develop independent assessment skills. This process has a positive impact on their personal development, metacognitive competencies and forms them as subjects of education. Monitoring activities carried out within the framework of pedagogical diagnostics allow teachers to conduct an in-depth analysis of each student or class based on previously obtained data. On this basis, lessons are adjusted, individual shortcomings are identified and necessary corrective measures are developed. Through this approach, the educational process is continuously developed and the quality of education is constantly monitored[8].

Conclusions and suggestions

The above analysis shows that pedagogical diagnostics in the context of online and hybrid education is not losing its relevance, but is being enriched with new forms and approaches based on digital technologies, artificial intelligence and interactive platforms. This process requires considering diagnostics not only as an assessment tool, but also as an important mechanism for managing the educational process that stimulates the personal development of students.

This state of modern education makes it necessary to put forward the following proposals and recommendations.

Conclusion

The development of digital education, especially in the context of online and hybrid education, has fundamentally changed the process of pedagogical diagnostics and acquired new opportunities. The activities of female educators play a central role in this process, playing an important role in forming a culture of assessment and improving the quality of education through the effective use of digital tools and artificial intelligence technologies. Flexible pedagogical diagnostic approaches - the harmonious use of formative, summative, adaptive and reflective assessment methods - allow identifying individual needs of students and stimulating their personal development. At the same time, the attention of female teachers to continuous professional development and the development of digital literacy further increases the effectiveness of the online and hybrid educational process.

Recommendations

1. Continuously improve the digital literacy of female teachers: In order to effectively use modern pedagogical diagnostic tools, it is necessary to provide teachers with regular professional development courses, online trainings and seminars on digital technologies.
2. Widespread introduction of formative assessment methods: The use of formative assessment tools at all stages of the educational process serves to determine the level of knowledge of students in real time, provide quick feedback and adapt the educational process.
3. Development of digital diagnostic methodologies across disciplines: Creating a digital assessment methodology adapted for each discipline and integrating it with digital platforms will ensure an objective and consistent assessment of the quality of education.
4. Implementation of a digital monitoring system for student activities: It is important to develop a monitoring system to identify students' achievements and shortcomings based on individual development maps and develop personally-oriented educational strategies.
5. Strengthening scientific and methodological approaches to pedagogical diagnostics: It is necessary to strengthen systematic and methodological work that ensures the use of digital tools and artificial intelligence technologies, and to widely implement best practices.
6. Implementation of personalized educational approaches: It is necessary to develop a differentiated approach and individual educational directions based on the results of diagnostics and apply them in the educational process.

In general, pedagogical diagnostics in online and hybrid education is emerging as an important tool for improving the quality of education, effectively managing the educational process, and improving teacher performance. Therefore, strengthening the methodological and scientific approach to this area, creating a system that is inextricably linked with digital tools, and introducing differentiated and personalized educational approaches based on diagnostic results should be one of the priorities of today's education.

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